

Does training and supervision act as mediators in health and safety of migrant construction workers?

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Abstract : The Indian construction industry has seen significant growth over the past two decades, with the sector contributing 8.6% of the total GDP. The industry has been a major driver of job creation and a major chunk of the population depends on the migrant workforce. Migrant workers are the most vulnerable members of society. However, migrant labour issues have been the object of many studies in India. Few have chosen to view the poor health and injury-prone migrant worker population in the Tamilnadu region, India.

This study recruited a sample of 140 respondents. Tools such as correlation, regression, exploratory factor analysis, and the mediation model using Macro process is used for the study. The findings proved that health and safety are interconnected, with training playing a significant role in both. Surprisingly, supervision had no mediation effect on safety but a considerable effect on health. The implication of the study is that not the actual supervision; it is the perception towards supervision that stops them from safety measures.

Keywords: *Health, Migrant workers, Safety, Supervision, Training*

Introduction

The Indian construction industry is significant for economic growth and development, and it is likely to occupy the largest market worldwide. Apart from its significance, a significant chunk of the population in this industry depends on the migrant workforce.

Migrant workers and their welfare are an age-old debate in economics and management. Though many labour laws and regulations exist, the reality is far from expected. This is because of gaps in enforcement, exploitation by contractors, lack of access to basic amenities, and the absence of any social security benefits. This results in a lack of job security and safety, low wages, and a lack of healthcare and other benefits, leading to an unjust system for the migrant workforce.

According to official estimates, Tamil Nadu is said to have 10.2 lakh migrant workers from West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Odisha, and northeastern region Anbuselvan, (2023). Features such as better wages, employment, marriage, and educational opportunities have made them stay for a more extended. Hence, the background and research setting of the study is in Tamilnadu, the Southern Part of India.

Although widely recognised as a ubiquitous problem in the construction industry, only a few have thought of a measure to help them. So, if a few companies seek to provide comprehensive solutions for protecting their workers, it would create and foster a friendly new environment.

There are multiple studies that talk about the health and safety of workers in different contexts. But still there is lack of perspective on health and safety of migrant workers of Tamil Nadu and understanding of underlying variables explaining the relationship between the health and safety Srinivasan, & Ilango, (2013); Venugopal et al., (2016); Tamarine et al., (2019). Hence, this study is considered for studying the relationship of health and safety of workers. This proposed study aims to assess the relationship between health and safety of workers and to examine the underlying mechanism that explains the relationship between health and safety of migrant labourers.

Thus the objectives of the study are:

Objective 1: To predict what specific factors contribute the most to establishing and maintaining health programs that lead to good safety.

Objective 2: To assess the relationship between the health and safety of workers in Tamil Nadu

Objective 3: To examine the underlying mechanism that explains the relationship between the health and safety of migrant labourers.

Interconnection between health and safety

There are studies that explain the interconnectedness between the health and safety of workers in different contexts. Oxenburgh et al., (2004) contends that safety and health go hand in hand and another study states that individuals will be healthy only if the environment is walkable and safe Doyle et al., (2006). In industrial transport, a study exhibited that there is an interrelationship significant between safety and health Atombo et al., (2017). Apart from these studies, there are literature that show that they are interconnected with each other Hu et al., (2020).

Interconnection of training between health and safety

The importance of training can be seen in the following areas. Firstly, training is the main characteristic of an occupational safety health system Awwad et al., (2016). Effective training is essential for employees as it provides adequate skills and knowledge to combat injuries and wounds Toole, (2002). Secondly, training helps to remove all the language barriers as most of the migrant workers fail to understand the local language as well as safety instructions well Li et al., (2018). Thirdly, it is useful for reducing the number of accidents and health hazards Nawaz et al., (2020). The fourth is that it can increase the competence of employees and inculcate a positive environment Fang & Wu, (2013). Fifth, is that training provides essential safe working practices for employees and an understanding of safety and health responsibilities in the workplace Bahn and Barratt-Pugh, (2012). Hence, training acts as a mediator between the safety and health of employees in the industry.

Interconnection of supervision between health and safety

Different authors have established the relationship of supervision with health, safety, emotional support, work flexibility, and control over bruises and injuries Patel and Jha, (2016). Hämmig

(2017), shows that there is an association between supervisor outcome and health. Low supervisor support and inadequate supervision trigger mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety, and other severe depressive symptoms, leading to unsafe acts Sinokki et al., (2009). Even the most recent study by Elmoujaddidi & Bachir (2020) argues that supervision is necessary for a safety and health climate. Hence, supervision acts as a mediator between the safety and health of employees in the industry.

The figure 1 displays the hypothesised relationship of health and safety of workers

Figure 1: The Hypothesised relationship of health and safety

The hypothesis proposed for this study is:

Hypothesis 1: Health has a positive effect on safety

Hypothesis 2: Training mediates the relationship between safety and health of employees

Hypothesis 3: Supervision mediates the relationship between safety and health of employees

Methodology

Scale design process

Primary data is used in the study. The questionnaire was designed through a standard scale development process Bagozzi et al., (1991). The questions were open ended. Likert scale was used, and it ranged from 0 to 5 –strongly disagree to strongly agree. A pilot study was done and out of which 20 items in the questionnaire, 15 items were taken for the study. The Cronbach Alpha was at an acceptable level for all the measures used in the study.

The inclusion criteria were related to demographic characteristics (age below forty years of age, male or female gender) and geographic features (Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Jharkhand, Odisha, and Assam). Convenience sampling is used to provide helpful information to answer questions and test hypotheses Creswell, (2003).

Data collection schedule

The samples were selected according keeping in mind of the population and so 250 was the desired sample size. The construction sites were located in significant parts of Tamil Nadu. The total period to collect data took around six months. So, to be precise, out of a total of 250 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 140 respondents gave prompt responses, and there were no missing values and errors.

Data analysis

Data collected were analysed using SPSS v.21.0. Apart from testing the reliability of the measures, demographic analysis of the sample; Correlation, Regression, principal component analysis and mediation analysis was conducted.

Data collected

The sample included participants from the age of 10 to 15 (1.4 percent) 16 to 20 years (25 percent), 21 to 25 years (49 percent), and 26 years-30 years (12.8 percent) and above 31-35 years are around 11 percent. This indicates that the majority of participants in this sample were between 21 and 25, with 25 percent being between 16 and 20 and 12.8 percent being between 26 and 30, thus showing the ages of the sample population.

Majority of the respondents consisted of men (98 percent) and only (2 percent) females. This shows that the industry is male centric in nature. Most of them hail from Bihar. The remaining belong to Uttar Pradesh (20% percent), Jharkhand (15% percent) and West Bengal (15% percent). A total of 13% of the workers are from the state of Orissa.

They earned around 1,00,000 to 2,00,000 lakh per year. There are very few people who earn more than 2,00,000 lakh per year.

The majority of the workers have not been at school say 49% percent. Nearly 35% of the workers have primary education say within 5 years of schooling and the rest have been to middle education (15 percent). Only 1 percent has been to secondary and higher secondary education.

Table 1: Correlation table of health and safety

Variables	Mean	SD	Correlations	
			Health	Safety
Health	3.04	0.436	1	0.758
Safety	1.94	0.316	0.758	1

Note: Correlations significant at .01 level = **

A correlation test was computed to assess the association between health and safety, and it indicates that there is a strong positive correlation between health and safety (r =0.758).

Table 2: Regression analysis of safety on health

Independent variable	Dependent Variable	F	R2	Beta
Safety	Health	186.465	0.575	0.758

Note: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Table 2 represents regression table. In order to provide more detailed analysis and an understanding, regression was used to justify the relationship. It indicated a sizeable positive effect on the safety and health of the employees ($r=0.575$). The adjusted R^2 shows that the safety explains 57.2% percent of the variance in health. It means that when an excellent safe environment is provided, the health of a migrant worker improves.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's test, Total variance table subsection of 15 items of workers' health

In this study, one of the objectives is to examine the underlying mechanism that explains the relationship between health and safety of migrant labourers. Hence, to explore it, Principal Component Analysis is necessary. To support the PCA, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's test of Sphericity is used. The results show subsection of 15 items of workers' health to principal components (PCA).

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.630
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.266E3
	df	105
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance table

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.795	31.964	31.964	4.795	31.964	31.964
2	2.399	15.992	47.956	2.399	15.992	47.956
3	1.719	11.463	59.419	1.719	11.463	59.419
4	1.326	8.839	68.258	1.326	8.839	68.258
5	1.063	7.088	75.346	1.063	7.088	75.346
6	.733	4.889	80.234			
7	.653	4.353	84.587			
8	.572	3.812	88.399			
9	.539	3.596	91.994			
10	.345	2.301	94.295			
11	.327	2.182	96.477			
12	.224	1.491	97.968			
13	.163	1.085	99.053			
14	.096	.643	99.696			

15	.046	.304	100.000			
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Component Matrix

The first shows a correlation matrix showing how each of the 15 items is associated with each of the other. The results are interpreted as

Figure 2: Scree plot subsection of 15 items of workers' health

Using Cattell (1966) scree test, it was decided to retain five elements for further investigation. An inspection of the scree plot revealed a clear break after the fifth component.

Table 4: Total Variance explained and rotated component matrix subsection of 15 items of workers' health

Using Cattell's (1966) Scree test, it was decided to retain five components for further investigation. According to Yaremko, Harari, Harrison, and Lynn (2013), varimax rotation is aimed at simplifying the factors themselves. Hence, it was performed to aid in the interpretation of these five elements.

Total variance explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.795	31.964	31.964	2.989	19.924	19.924
2	2.399	15.992	47.956	2.739	18.259	38.183
3	1.719	11.463	59.419	2.403	16.023	54.205
4	1.326	8.839	68.258	1.704	11.362	65.567
5	1.063	7.088	75.346	1.467	9.779	75.346
6	0.733	4.889	80.234			
7	0.653	4.353	84.587			
8	0.572	3.812	88.399			
9	0.539	3.596	91.994			
10	0.345	2.301	94.295			

11	0.327	2.182	96.477			
12	0.224	1.491	97.968			
13	0.163	1.085	99.053			
14	0.096	0.643	99.696			
15	0.046	0.304	100			

Rotated Component matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Sanitation	0.844	-0.026	-0.013	-0.032	0.025
Day to day activities	0.666	0.401	0.061	0.427	-0.208
Moderate activities	0.618	0.382	-0.032	0.55	-0.09
Heavy Activities	0.521	-0.115	0.122	0.494	0.468
Heart Disease	-0.192	-0.054	0.861	0.01	0.063
Limbic pain	-0.103	0.181	0.834	0.015	0.03
Concomitant effects	0.485	-0.054	0.672	-0.04	-0.081
Working hours	0.048	0.493	-0.013	0.259	-0.625
Social Gatherings	0.067	-0.027	-0.016	0.921	-0.097
Paint	-0.726	-0.316	0.12	-0.16	0.17
Access - Drinking water	-0.02	0.728	-0.051	-0.108	-0.135
Excessive noise	0.474	0.7	0.287	0.057	0.115
excessive heat	0.321	0.554	0.618	0.025	0.023
Diesel fumes	0.134	0.819	0.115	0.123	0.159
First aid	-0.133	0.193	0.013	-0.022	0.835

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

The Rotated Factor Matrix table 4, which contains these loadings, is critical for understanding the results of the analysis Leech et al., (2013). The rotated solution revealed the presence of a simple structure with five components showing several heavy loadings. The five factors solution explained a total of 19.92 percent of the variance with Component 1, Component 2 contributing 18.26 per cent, Component 3 contributing 16.02 per cent, Component 4 contributing 11.36 and component 5 contributing 9.78 per cent. The primary loadings of element 1 are items (sanitation, day to day physical activities, moderate activities, vigorous activities), component 2 consists of the item (exposure to paints, access to clean drinking water, exposure to loud noises and diesel fumes), and component 3 consists of (congestion in lungs, muscular ailments, concomitant effects, exposure to excessive heat), component 4 consists of interaction in social gatherings, component 5 consists of working hours and first aid.

Table 5. KMO and Bartlett's test, Total variance table subsection of 15 items of workers' safety

Principal Component Analysis is necessary to examine the underlying mechanism that explains the relationship between health and safety of migrant labourers. To support the PCA, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett’s test of Sphericity is used. The results in table 5 show subsection of 15 items of workers' safety and it consists of Correlation matrix, KMO and Bartlett's test, Total variance table, Component Matri

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.566
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	923.803
	df	105
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance table

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.9	25.998	25.998	3.9	25.998	25.998
2	2.184	14.563	40.561	2.184	14.563	40.561
3	1.938	12.92	53.481	1.938	12.92	53.481
4	1.202	8.015	61.496	1.202	8.015	61.496
5	1.037	6.916	68.412	1.037	6.916	68.412
6	1.001	6.672	75.085	1.001	6.672	75.085
7	0.762	5.08	80.164			
8	0.749	4.993	85.157			
9	0.656	4.373	89.53			
10	0.516	3.442	92.972			
11	0.343	2.288	95.26			
12	0.305	2.031	97.291			
13	0.163	1.089	98.38			
14	0.144	0.958	99.338			
15	0.099	0.662	100			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was 0.57, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity reached statistical significance, supporting the factorability of the correlation. Principal components analysis revealed the presence of six components with eigenvalues exceeding 1, explaining 26 percent, 14.56 percent, 12.92 percent, 8.01 percent, 6.92 percent, and 6.67percent of the variance, respectively.

Figure 3: Scree plot subsection of 15 items of workers' safety

The scree plot shows that after the first two components, increases in the eigenvalues decline, and revealed a clear break after the sixth component. Both the Scree Plot and the eigenvalues support the conclusion that these variables can be reduced to six components. Varimax rotation was performed to aid in the interpretation of these elements.

Table 6: Total Variance explained and rotated component matrix subsection of 15 items of workers' safety

According to Yaremko et al., (2013), rotation of factor axes in the principal-components analysis is identified as the initial extraction of factors. It is used to obtain interpretable and straightforward factors. The rotated solution is presented in table 6.

Total variance table

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.9	25.998	25.998	2.645	17.631	17.631
2	2.184	14.563	40.561	2.616	17.441	35.072
3	1.938	12.92	53.481	2.259	15.059	50.131
4	1.202	8.015	61.496	1.39	9.266	59.397
5	1.037	6.916	68.412	1.213	8.088	67.485
6	1.001	6.672	75.085	1.14	7.6	75.085
7	0.762	5.08	80.164			
8	0.749	4.993	85.157			
9	0.656	4.373	89.53			
10	0.516	3.442	92.972			

11	0.343	2.288	95.26			
12	0.305	2.031	97.291			
13	0.163	1.089	98.38			
14	0.144	0.958	99.338			
15	0.099	0.662	100			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix						
	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Receive compensation	-0.238	-0.085	0.21	-0.798	0.024	-0.091
Hit by falling materials	-0.018	0.082	0.139	0.12	0.018	0.909
Method assessment and risk	0.071	0.814	0.308	0.175	0.136	-0.125
Received shock	-0.117	-0.151	-0.747	0.06	-0.267	-0.14
Major/fatal accidents	-0.141	-0.078	-0.908	0.049	0.005	-0.082
Rescued from debris	0.036	0.7	-0.013	-0.05	-0.133	0.231
Work platform	0.645	0.142	0.545	0.144	-0.061	0.065
Heat & weather conditions	-0.42	0.02	0.255	0.553	-0.147	0.052
Direct contact with injury	0.884	0.052	0.072	0.044	0.04	0.009
Direct contact with scaffolding	0.822	0.324	0.124	0.062	-0.093	-0.08
Attend training programmes	0.552	-0.244	0.232	-0.383	-0.112	0.417
Follow safety measures	0.045	0.45	0.335	0.429	0.405	-0.001
Supervisor guides and promotes safety measures	-0.057	-0.117	0.109	-0.068	0.904	-0.006
Wear PPE	0.163	0.878	0.084	0.13	-0.126	-0.076
Report safety problems	0.403	0.496	-0.39	-0.122	0.244	0.128

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

The six factors solution in table 6 explained Component 1 consisting of 17.63 per cent, Component 2 contributing 17.44 per cent, Component 3 contributing 15.06per cent, Component 4 contributing 9.27 per cent, component 5 comprising of 8.09 per cent and component 6 providing 7.6 per cent. The main loading of the component includes items (compensation, method statement, rescued from debris, working in high place and wearing personal protective equipment), component 2 consists of items (attend, report), component 3 consists of items such as receiving shock and respondents who have met fatal accidents and who fell unconscious, component 4 consists of supervisor promoting supervising safety measures, component 5 consists of respondents who receive compensation and component 6 consists of labourers who been hit by falling materials.

From all these analyses, it shows that there are 5 items for health and 6 items for safety. Hence, mediation analysis is used to know the underlying mechanism that explains the relationship

between health and safety of migrant labourers Process macro. According to Henseler et al., (2016), mediation analysis is used to understand the development of processes.

Figure 4: The model of the relation between the health and safety of labourers with training and supervision as the mediators

In the final stage of analysis, there is a need of testing mediating role using process model to determine the significance of the indirect effect of training and supervision on health and safety. Output from the SPSS version of Process model is represented in Figure 4. Health is a sign (positive predictor of safety ($b=0.491$, $S.E = 0.046$, $p < 0.01$). This coefficient reflects the direct effect of health on safety. Training is a significant and positive predictor of health ($b= 0.490$, $S.E = 0.095$, $p = 0.000$) and safety ($b= 0.299$, $S.E = 0.045$, $P = 0.000$). However, supervision is significant and positive predictor of health ($b= 0.361$, $S.E = 0.108$, $p = 0.001$). But it is significant and negative predictor of safety ($b= -0.080$, $S.E = 0.030$, $p = 0.000$).

Discussions

The results infer that the majority of the respondents are young. Surprisingly there are workers who are less than 18 years working in the construction sites. Many of the workers stay with families and hence, young children work to support their families. The industry is also male centric in nature. The disparity in the number of males and females in the industry indicates that there is a lack of gender diversity, which suggests that there may be a barrier preventing women from entering and succeeding in the construction industry. Bihar has a larger proportion of respondents than the other states. Regarding their income, majority of the workers earn from 1,00,000 to 2,00,000 lakh per year. This could be that they have fewer opportunities as other workers. The major proportion of the respondents do not have any knowledge about school not have attended schooling. This shows their financial burden to support their families.

The results prove that there is an association and relationship among the variables and that is Safety has a positive effect on health. Process Macro used showed that training mediates the relationship between safety and health. It means that training is positive predictor for health and safety of employees. There is an interesting finding supervision mediates the relationship between safety and health of employees but it is negatively related to safety and positively related to health of employees.

Limitations and future scope

The study is limited to 140 respondents, and there is a scope in the future for increasing the sample size. The questionnaire framed by the researcher can be used for a more thorough understanding of the policy implications connected with the health and safety of workers. In the long run, it can be used as a model for ensuring the health and safety of workers with training and supervision.

Implication and conclusion

The result indicates that health and safety are interrelated to each other. It means that even the most risk-prone migrant workers, once they are entitled to a well-thought-out comprehensive health programme, lead to efficient and injury-free workers. These results can be generalised to any projects on the construction site and across regions.

The analysis of workers reveals the following inferences. First, the most comprehensive training provided the lowest number of work-related accidents compared to supervision. This suggests that training is the most effective way to prevent accidents, as it gives workers the skills to work safely and efficiently. Additionally, it helps workers understand the safety protocols and procedures that need to be followed to reduce the risk of injury or accidents. This is because training provides workers with the knowledge and skills to identify potential risks and develop the skills to work safely and efficiently.

The analysis suggests that workers prefer training on supervision regarding safety. It may be because training is conducted only once a month or twice a year, whereas supervision is conducted regularly, so they dislike it. This finding was also made consistent to the previous studies Williams et al., (2010; Awwad et al., (2016)

The other interpretation is that when there are supervision arrangements, health increases, and safety is minimal. This finding was contrary to the studies conducted by researchers Hämmig (2017); Elmoujaddidi & Bachir, (2020). As the supervisor serves as a liaison for workers, they oversee and evaluate workers on worksites. These acts make them cautious and diversion from safety measures leading to slips, injuries, and accidents. If a supervisor is not present enough or is too overbearing, then employees; reaction will only be fear, resentment, and displeasure in their work Duffy et al., (2002). Hence, to be precise, it is not actual supervision; it is the perception towards supervision that stops them from safety measures. These findings have made a breakthrough in the study.

The study recommends the following suggestions. Companies such as Apple and Amazon have already started and practising the principle, Hire the man, teach the skill and supervise Carmine Gallo, (2015). Hence, it is necessary to integrate training programs into a generalised system that could help the migrant worker be as productive as the rest of the workforce.

The next recommendation is that lousy supervision should not be neglected in the workplace. It can be done by proper monitoring and scrutinisation. Implementing supervisory boards and inspecting worksites are the measures to manage the supervisors' activities.

Last but not least, utmost attention should be given to employee's safety and health. As Shri Santosh Kumar Gangwar rightly said, healthy individuals and fewer accidents lead to a productive workforce that enhances economic growth Government of India, (2019). Indeed, once these suggestions and measures are implemented, it would make stakeholders see a new and more profitable enterprise unfold in front of them, which attract record-breaking investments to their state and the overall growth of the nation.

Of the many Western studies that have focused on issues of safety and health of workers, few have been entirely relevant concerning the Indian migrant workers in and around the State of Tamil Nadu, which ranks as the second-largest state economy in India. For a company to become truly successful no matter where their location is, it is important that companies in the future oblige with this idea of: "Hire the man, teach the skill and supervise."

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APPENDIX - QUESTIONNAIRE FOR LABOURERS

A. Personal Profile

1. Age
2. Gender
3. Native place
4. Income
5. Educational attainment

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements by putting a tick mark or circle in the appropriate box

B. Health

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I am provided with proper sanitation on the work premises					
2. My health prevents me from engaging in day-to-day physical activities					
3. My health prevents me from engaging in moderate activities such as moving a table and climbing stairs					
4. My health prevents me from engaging in heavy activities such as running and lifting heavy objects					
5. My health experience congestion in the lungs and heart-related diseases.					
6. My health experience muscular ailments, aches & limbic pain.					
7. My health experience concomitant effects such as fatigue, tiredness, boredom, monotony, and post-traumatic stress due to work.					
8. I work more than working hours (Factories Act 1948 is eight hours per day) to support your family					

9.I have problems interfered with social activities and social gatherings (like visiting friends and relatives)					
10.I am exposed to paint, pesticides, and dust					
11. I have access to clean drinking water					
12. I am exposed to loud noises					
13. I am exposed to excessive/ uncomfortable heat					
14. I am exposed to diesel fumes & carbon dioxide					
15. I am provided first-aid & medical facilities					

C. Safety

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Almost always
1. I have received compensation for injuries or persistent illness					
2. I have been hit by falling materials					
3. I have been provided a method statement and risk assessment					
4. I have received shock					
5. I have met with major or fatal accidents					
6. I have been rescued from debris					
7. I work in a high place without a work platform or opening protection					
8. I feel unconscious due to heat and weather conditions					
9. I make direct contact with the source of injuries such as structures or construction equipment and body in horizontal motion such as carrying materials or cleaning up while working					

10. I make direct contact with scaffolding, openings, roofs, roof trusses, and work platforms					
11. I attend training programmes					
12. I follow safety measures at work (unable to comprehend Tamil)					
13. My supervisor guides and promotes safety measures during work					
14. I wear personal protective equipment					
15. I feel free to report safety problems					